

GROQ-seq Technical Status Report

January 2025

Transcription Factors	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Proteases	✓	✓	✓	✓	
RNA Polymerases	✓	✓	✓		
tRNA Synthetases	✓	✓			
scFVs	✓				
Histidine Kinases	✓				

In its first year, the GROQ-seq initiative made key engineering advances that improved assay performance, cross-site reproducibility, and support for complex protein functions.

- DHFR circuits replace TetA, enabling >100× dynamic range and broader function support.
- Standardized media from Teknova improved growth consistency across sites.
- Modular plasmid parts allow flexible, scalable circuit design using Golden Gate assembly.

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Overview

The Align Foundation and NIST have collaborated to develop an experimental platform and unified data ontology for collecting and sharing open-access data on diverse protein functions. This initiative is designed to enable the development of predictive models that link sequence to function.

Data generation is based on the growth-based quantitative sequencing (GROQ-seq) platform—a simple yet adaptable system that can be easily expanded to encompass new functions. This high-throughput experimental platform enables quantitative functional characterization data of hundreds of thousands of proteins per experiment, at an estimated cost of \$0.05 per sequence.

To support data generation at scale, six academic labs are collaborating with NIST, The Francis Crick Institute, and the DAMP Lab as data collection sites. Seven protein functions have been proposed, reviewed by domain-specific experts in the research community, and are currently undergoing circuit tuning and validation for platform onboarding.

This technical report summarizes key updates from the first year of engineering. During development, deviations from the original proposal accelerated circuit tuning, improved cross-site standardization, and enhanced data quality.

Onboarding Status

To date, there are seven collaborator-driven protein functions in our research pipeline. Proposals for each function are published after undergoing review¹⁻⁷. These functions then undergo a standardized onboarding process to validate them for our GROQ-seq platform (Table 1). The onboarding of these functions has been staggered to accommodate bandwidth at primary data collection facilities.

	Plasmid Design The high-level plasmid architecture containing the gene circuit that connects function to growth is finalized and ready to be synthesized for testing.	Initial Response Measured The gene circuit's responsiveness to high and low signal has been measured using either gene variants or inducer concentrations, demonstrating its functionality and readiness for optimization.	Circuit Optimized The gene circuit's dynamic range has been fully expanded through optimization of RBS and promoter strengths to regulate expression and/or the fine-tuning of inducer concentrations. The circuit is now responsive to a wide range of functional levels.	Calibration Ladder Finalized Calibration variants are selected to span the dynamic range of the gene circuit, either by engineering variants with a wide range of function and/or by modulating inducer concentrations. Once measured in singleplex, each calibration variant is assigned a specific barcode and is included in subsequent pooled assays.	Pooled Assay Validated Calibration variants have been pooled and run through the GROO-seq platform. When compared to their singleplex measurements, a strong correlation is observed, confirming the robustness of the GROO-seq pooled assay. These results validate the assay's readiness for running variant libraries alongside calibration controls.
Transcription Factors Read Proposal Proposal Leaders: • Simon D'Oelsnitz (Harvard Medical School) • David Ross (NIST)					
Proteases Read Proposal Proposal Leaders: • Erika DeBenedictis (Francis Crick Institute) • David Ross (NIST)					
T7 RNA Polymerases Read Proposal Proposal Leaders: • Erika DeBenedictis (Francis Crick Institute) • Lily Nematollahi (Francis Crick Institute)					
tRNA Synthetases Read Proposal Proposal Leaders: • Ross Thyer (Rice University) • David Ross (NIST)					
Histidine Kinases Read Proposal Proposal Leaders: • Katie Hatsat (UC San Francisco) • William DeGrado (UC San Francisco) • David Ross (NIST)					
Single-chain Antibody Fragments Read Proposal Proposal Leaders: • Ronald Koder (City College of New York) • David Ross (NIST)					
Dihydrofolate reductase Read Proposal Proposal Leader: • Kimberly A. Reynolds (University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center)					

Table 1: To-date results for each stage of the GROO-seq onboarding process illustrated by function.

Engineering strategy updates

Use of dihydrofolate reductase for growth-coupled circuits

Our original proposal envisioned using the tetracycline (Tet)/tetracycline resistance gene (TetA) system to couple protein function to the growth of bacterial cells⁸. However, during testing, we found that the trimethoprim (TMP)/dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) system has several advantages over Tet/TetA, chiefly, a higher dynamic range (Fig. 1) along with other benefits outlined in Table 2.

As a result, we chose to switch to using ecDHFR for the transcription factor, tRNA synthetase, and histidine kinase projects, and a split mDHFR for the protease and single-chain antibody fragment projects, where a split DHFR is required.

	Tetracycline resistance gene (TetA)	Dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR)
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proven use⁹ No active decrease of DNA barcode count Possible higher sensitivity (related to narrow dynamic range) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Larger dynamic range, >100-fold at a single TMP concentration Applicable to wider range of protein function types with split DHFR systems Smaller, cytosolic protein (159 aa)
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Narrow dynamic range, ~10-fold at a single tet concentration Difficult to tune, requires very low expression TetA is a large membrane protein (401 aa) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use in quantitative pooled assays not yet as well proven Active decrease of DNA barcode count

Table 2: Comparison of using tetracycline vs the TMP/DHFR system in function circuits.

Figure 1: Comparison of TetA and ecDHFR as antibiotic resistance markers. A) With TetA, as expression levels increase, the fitness increases rapidly. B) With ecDHFR, fitness levels increase more gradually with expression, even at high levels, enabling a larger dynamic range.

Use of commercially manufactured media

We originally intended for each data collection site to prepare its own media. However, we found that even the production of standard media types, such as M9, led to substantial growth differences in cell growth when produced at different facilities (Fig. 3).

For this reason, we subcontracted media production to a commercial manufacturer, Teknova (Hollister, CA), and are requiring that all automation sites running the GROQ-seq platform use this standardized media. Through this process, we are able to maintain rigorous quality control of the media product and enhance reproducibility of cell growth across sites. Subsequent experimentation has revealed additional, strain-dependent media limitations. For libraries measured in DH10B, we observed a decrease in growth when using Teknova media older than approximately one month. This growth impact was not observed for MG1655-based libraries, even using media exceeding three months old. We hypothesize that as the media ages, there are changes that decrease the bioavailable concentrations of the amino acid components, which eventually become growth limiting. We will continue to evaluate the impacts of this effect and work to develop more robust processes.

Figure 2: Example of differences in growth between three batches of M9 media prepared at two facilities. One batch was produced at NIST and shipped to the Crick for analysis, the other two batches were prepared and analyzed on-site at the Crick. Each color indicates a different media preparation, with each dashed line representing a technical replicate.

Defining default sub-library designs for pilot-scale measurements

After each GROQ-seq function assay is validated, an initial pilot library of ~100k variants is measured. This pilot library is often composed of a variety of sub-libraries, produced using different library design techniques. We have implemented a default approach for initial library design, specifically:

1. a sub-library containing all single amino acid substitutions, insertions, and deletions, and
2. a sub-library containing random multi-mutations (targeting 3-4 mutations per gene).

We have found commercial solutions to generate these sub-libraries using the SSVL library product from Twist Bioscience (South San Francisco, CA) and the error-prone PCR product from Genscript (Piscataway, NJ). For now, each function's pilot library will contain these two default sub-libraries; however, as subsequent pilot and large-scale libraries are measured, we will continue to evaluate the effectiveness of the various library design techniques implemented to determine the most effective strategies for exploring the functional landscape.

Modular plasmid design

Our original proposal involved a standardized plasmid architecture; however, we found that correctly tuning circuits for each protein function is a task that benefits from more flexibility than we had originally envisioned. We continue to use a standardized barcode region across all plasmids, which ensures that the DNA sequencing workflow remains consistent, but we are no longer using a standardized plasmid backbone or a required order for groups of components. To enable diverse plasmid architectures, we have shifted from a standardized architecture to a modular design, where a wide range of plasmid components can be incorporated within modules that facilitate a streamlined approach to outsourcing the downstream cloning with Clutch Bio (Hayward, CA) (Fig. 4). This modular approach enables a high level of component diversity, including different plasmid copy numbers, tunable promoters, bicistronic RBSs, etc., and enables increasingly complex genetic systems to work within the same experimental platform. The modular design uses predefined basic parts with set overhangs for Golden Gate assembly (Table 2). These parts can be combined or further subdivided to suit the needs of each function.

Figure 3: Schematics for the cloning strategy employed in the **A)** protease and **B)** transcription factor projects. Each part type is represented by a number within the plasmid and the corresponding part description on the outside of the plasmid. Note that both projects use common modular parts (1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6), each being composed of predefined Golden Gate overhangs surrounding a modifiable variable region. These basic parts can be combined (e.g., the 5,6,1,2a part used in the protease project) or further subdivided as needed (e.g., the 2b, 2c, and 2d subparts each representing an oligo pool used to create a library of TEV protease variants). Part types and descriptions are outlined in Table 2.

Type	Description	5' OH	3' OH	Ex: Transcription Factor Part Description	Ex: Protease Part Description
1	Flex 1	GACT	TATG	Transcription Factor promoter (expression cassette) & 1st half of selection cassette (includes promoter)	Protease promoter (expression cassette) & 1st half of selection cassette (split at promoter)
2	ORF	TATG	TAAT	Transcription Factor Gene	Not used. Sub-divided into parts below
2a	ORF (sub-part 1)	TATG	ATCT	Not used	Maltose binding protein + linker
2b	ORF (sub-part 2)	ATCT	GGGA		TEV protease gene section 1
2c	ORF (sub-part 3)	GGGA	TCAA		TEV protease gene section 2
2d	ORF (sub-part 4)	TCAA	TAAT		TEV protease gene section 3
3a	Barcode 1	TAAT	CACA	First half barcode	First half barcode
3b	Barcode 2	CACA	AGGT	Second half barcode	Second half barcode
4	Backbone 1	AGGT	GCCA	First half of backbone (split at KanR)	First half of backbone (split at KanR)
5	Backbone 2	GCCA	TTGA	Second half of backbone (split at KanR)	Second half of backbone (split at KanR)
6	Flex 2	TTGA	GACT	2nd half of selection cassette components (minus promoter)	2nd half of selection cassette components (split at promoter)

Table 3: Descriptions of the predefined basic parts used across functions for Golden Gate assembly.

Tuning using inducers rather than constitutive elements

Our original proposal avoided the use of inducible promoters because of the perceived technical risks associated with standardizing inducer concentrations across sites. However, we found that tuning circuits for each of many different protein functions is accelerated by the use of inducible promoters, rather than relying on cloning and sequence verifying plasmids for each of many different constitutive promoter strengths. We now rely on inducible promoters by default, and many of the functions now use the Marionette strain to more easily enable the use of these promoters¹⁰.

Accounting for *E. coli* strain restriction and modification effects

Our initial plan was for each function team to select a single *E. coli* strain to use for both plasmid library maintenance (maintenance strain) and for its GROQ-Seq assay (assay strain). However, based on a recent preprint¹¹, we determined that all functions should use a *recA*⁻ strain (i.e., a typical cloning strain) for maintenance to prevent plasmid multimer formation. This change had minimal impact on functions already using *recA*⁻ assay strains, such as proteases and scFVs, which rely on the *recA*⁻ Marionette-Clo strain¹⁰ (Fig. 2a). However, it introduced challenges for functions like transcription factor and histidine kinase projects, which require knockout assay strains typically derived from MG1655, a *recA*⁺ strain. These functions now needed a separate *recA*⁻ maintenance strain instead of using a single strain for both maintenance and assay purposes.

Initially, functions relying on MG1655 assay strains planned to use DH10B (*recA*⁻) as the maintenance strain (DH10B → MG1655). However, we found that this approach would not be successful¹², as MG1655 (*R*⁺*M*⁺) is restrictive and actively degrades unmodified incoming DNA from DH10B (*R*⁻*M*⁻), leading to poor transformation efficiency. Our updated plan is to use DH5α (*R*⁻*M*⁺) as a *recA*⁻ maintenance strain for functions where the assay strain is *R*⁺ (e.g., knockout MG1655 strains used in transcription factor and histidine kinase projects) (Fig. 2b). The use of DH5α ensures compatibility with plasmid libraries from various cloning strains and provides good transformation efficiency into MG1655.

Suggested Reading

Below is a suggested curated reading list to better understand this document and its context:

This technical status report describes implementation of the GROQ-Seq platform as proposed to Align's Open Datasets Initiative. Read the original proposal here:

“Design of a generalized platform for gathering protein sequence → function datasets at scale”

February 2024, Zenodo

The cover features the 'ALIGN TO INNOVATE' logo at the top. The title is 'Design of a generalized platform for gathering protein sequence → function datasets at scale'. A central diagram shows a workflow: 'Many Functions' leads to 'gene & variant' and 'Single DNA Colocalization Process', which then leads to 'sequencing'. Below the diagram, a text box describes the platform: 'A proposed platform for gathering large protein sequence-to-function datasets.' It lists three key features: 1) 'Uses a pooled growth-based assay to quantify protein function for ~ \$0.05/sequence', 2) 'Applicable to a wide variety of protein functions', and 3) 'New functions can be onboarded by validating a gene circuit and establishing a set of calibration variants.' The cover also includes a 'Reviewed' badge and a 'bioRxiv' logo.

Read more about how large-scale genotype-phenotype mapping can reveal unexpected functional behaviors in allosteric proteins—such as the band-stop phenotype in LacI variants— here:

“The genotype-phenotype landscape of an allosteric protein”

March 2021, *Molecular Systems Biology*

The cover features the 'molecular systems biology' logo at the top right. The title is 'The genotype-phenotype landscape of an allosteric protein'. The authors listed are Drew S Tack, Peter D Tonner, Abe Pressman, Nathan D Olson, Saha F Levy, Eugenia F Romantseva, Nina Aljovic, Olga Vasilyeva, and David Ross. The cover includes an 'Article' badge and a 'bioRxiv' logo. The abstract discusses the allosteric mechanism of LacI and the development of a generalized quantitative description. The introduction explains the allosteric property of biomolecules and the experimental setup for quantifying gene expression in response to ligand concentration. The equation $G(x) = \frac{C_0 - C_0 x}{1 + (x/K)^n}$ is shown, where $G(x)$ is basal gene expression, C_0 is gene expression at saturating ligand concentration, x is the effective concentration of ligand, and K is the effective concentration of ligand that results in gene repression.

References

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6. Kelly, P., Cortade, D., Reynolds, K. A. & Filipowska, K. Design of growth-coupled measurements of Dihydrofolate Reductase in vivo biochemistry. *Zenodo (manuscript in preparation)*.
7. Kelly, P. et al. Design of growth-coupled measurements of T7 RNA Polymerase function. *Zenodo (manuscript in preparation)*.
8. Cortade, D. et al. Design of a generalized platform for gathering protein sequence → function datasets at scale. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13909104> (2024).
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11. Vaisbourd, E., Bren, A., Alon, U. & Glass, D. S. Preventing plasmid multimer formation in commonly used synthetic biology plasmids. *Synthetic Biology* (2024).
12. Does anyone familiar the restriction modification system in DH10B and DH5alpha E.coli strain? *ResearchGate* <https://www.researchgate.net/post/Does-anyone-familiar-the-restriction-modification-system-in-DH10B-and-DH5alpha-Ecoli-strain>.